

Neutrosophic Reliability Assessment of Hydroelectric Power Plant using Universal Generating Function Technique

*Kanak Saini, *Monika Saini, *Ashish Kumar & \$Dinesh Kumar Saini¹

*Department of Mathematics & Statistics, Manipal University Jaipur, Jaipur-303007, India

\$Department of IOT & Intelligent Systems, Manipal University Jaipur, Jaipur-303007, India

*Email.: ashish.kumar@jaipur.manipal.edu

Abstract: The main objective of present study is to assess the reliability measures of a hydroelectric power plant under neutrosophic environment. There are several reliability evaluations like Markovian approach, Semi-Markovian approach, etc. However, these techniques fail to deal with the fuzziness of the data due to impreciseness. For this purpose, here universal generating function technique is used to evaluate the reliability and mean time to failure of hydroelectric power plant. The hydroelectric power plant is a complex structure having six subsystems having configured in series structure. The subsystem, namely turbine configured according to parallel redundancy. Each neutrosophic variable is illustrated by a triangular neutrosophic number and follows the Weibull distribution. Numerical results of reliability and MTTF are derived for understanding the system's behaviour using triangular neutrosophic number. To highlight the importance of MTTF results are also represented graphically.

Keywords: Neutrosophic reliability, triangular neutrosophic number, mean time to failure, sustainable manufacturing system, universal generating function.

1. Introduction

Reliability in systems plays a major role, as it ensures constant performance, reduces failures, and increases user trust. There are several methods, such as the Markov technique, fault tree analysis, semi-Markovian technique and reliability block diagram, which are used for the reliability evaluation of process industries. However, these techniques fail to deal with the fuzziness and uncertainty of the data due to imprecision. Uncertainty theory is a branch of mathematics that deals with modeling and analyzing uncertain behavior, like fuzziness and randomness. The fuzzy set theory was first introduced by Zadeh [1], and since then, the various properties of fuzzy uncertainty theory have evolved in a new direction. Fuzzy set theory can handle uncertainties arising from vagueness or partial belonging, but it cannot deal with all types of uncertainties, especially in real-life problems having incomplete information. Atanassov [2] modified the fuzzy set theory to create intuitionistic fuzzy set theory. In this modified intuitionistic fuzzy theory, the concept of both membership function and non-membership function was introduced. These membership functions and non-membership functions can measure the degree of belonging and non-belongingness in a set. Liu and Yuan [3] applied the concept of triangular fuzzy numbers and an intuitionistic fuzzy set theory to introduce a triangular intuitionistic fuzzy set. Anand and Bharatraj [4] conducted the number theory analysis of triangular fuzzy numbers. Seikh et al. [5] discussed triangular fuzzy numbers from an intuitionistic fuzzy perspective. In this study, some basic rules and non-linear operations of triangular intuitionistic fuzzy numbers (TIFN) are developed to establish the relation between two TIFNs. The average ranking index was introduced, and a method was explained to approximate a TIFN to a closely estimated interval number. As the traditional set theory and fuzzy set theory failed to handle many situations involving uncertain information, the neutrosophic set theory was introduced to address these uncertainties more effectively. While fuzzy set theory only deals with truth values but,

neutrosophic set theory overcomes these limitations by dealing with three components-truth, indeterminacy, and falsity. Smarandache [6,7,8,9] established the concept of a neutrosophic set and considered the truth membership function, indeterminacy function, and falsity function. It can manage uncertainty and imprecision in data more distinctly. This theory can fulfill all the limitations of traditional fuzzy set theory, as it can solve real-world problems more effectively and be used in decision-making. Several researchers proposed extensions of the neutrosophic set to handle different types of problems [10,11,12]. Though very few works reported on the reliability evaluation of industrial systems under neutrosophic environment. Mahapatra and Roy [13] analyzed fuzzy system reliability by considering the reliability of each component as a triangular intuitionistic fuzzy number and described the expressions for fuzzy reliability of series and parallel systems. An electric network model of a dark room is considered and the reliability of each component of this system is measured as triangular intuitionistic fuzzy numbers. Garg et al. [14] analyzed the reliability of industrial systems. The lambda-tau methodology was used, and the uncertain and imprecise data was analyzed through the intuitionistic fuzzy set (IFS) theory and the results were compared with existing traditional crisp and fuzzy methodologies results. Guilani et al. [15] studied the reliability analysis of non-repairable three-state systems by introducing a new technique based on the Markov process and compared it to traditional methods like universal generation function (UGF) and recursive algorithms. Li et al. [16] used traditional universal generating function (UGF) to improve the reliability and availability of multi-state system and random fuzzy variables were used by an extension hybrid UGF (HUGF). Gao et al. [17] reflected the factors like load, strength, operational states, and probabilities as a fuzzy factor and design the reliability models for multi-state systems. To design the model components and systems, the universal generating function method was used. Chakraborty et al. [18] explored neutrosophic numbers, including linear and non-linear generalized triangular neutrosophic numbers. The concept of de-eutrophication was also presented and used these concepts to imprecise project evaluation and route selection problems. Ebeling [19] described reliability as the probability that a system or component will perform its required functions under stated conditions for a specified period of time. Measurement of reliability is quite challenging due to circumstances like system behavior change, human error, and the lack of proper data availability (insufficient data). For the success of any product/system, reliability plays a very important role. To enhance the design of any system, traditional reliability methods are commonly used by researchers. The involvement of complexity, human behaviour, and natural phenomena's inconsistency/uncertainties arises in the failure data of systems. In such situations traditional probability-based models face difficulties in dealing with uncertainties in data. The uncertainties in failure probabilities cannot be clearly measured by these traditional methods. To deal with this limitation, various fuzzy sets, intuitionistic fuzzy sets, Fermatean fuzzy sets, Pythagorean fuzzy sets, etc., were used to handle uncertainty in reliability analysis. Alhasan and Smarandache [20] focused on neutrosophic Weibull distribution and its family. Various variations of this distribution are also explained such as Neutrosophic Inverse Weibull, Neutrosophic Rayleigh, Neutrosophic three-parameter Weibull, Neutrosophic Beta Weibull, Neutrosophic five Weibull, Neutrosophic six Weibull distributions and help to deal with problems having uncertain, vague, and imprecise. Saini et al. [21] presented the simplified version of a single-valued neutrosophic number (single-valued trapezoidal neutrosophic number). It uses the process called de-neutrophication for practical applications which convert neutrosophic number into a crisp number. Mondal et al. [22] studied a mining safety model by using the neutrosophic sets, triangular single-valued neutrosophic numbers, trapezoidal single-valued neutrosophic numbers, and neutrosophic differential equations. Alamin et al. [23] emphasizes the value of neutrosophic set theory in discrete systems. The homogeneous linear differential equations were solved under neutrosophic environment, and the initial conditions and coefficients are used as neutrosophic numbers. Saini and Ahirwar [24] applied interval-valued trapezoidal neutrosophic numbers for solving neutrosophic transportation problems (NTP) during uncertain and inconsistent situations. Kamal et al. [25] suggested a decision-making model to enhance the reliability of complex systems. The components are repaired or replaced during

maintenance to make the system more efficient. The best results were found by using a combination of four-valued neutrosophic technique and fuzzy logic. Ram et al. [26] evaluates the reliability of solar panel k-out-of-n systems using universal generating function. Kumar et al. [27] studied a gas turbine system and triangular neutrosophic sets and its applications were used to control uncertainties and enhance its reliability. Mondal et al. [28] focuses on the safety of nuclear power plants by handling the uncertainties using single-valued triangular neutrosophic numbers. Chachra et al. [29] used hesitant and dual hesitant fuzzy sets to examine the reliability of the summer air-conditioner system. The system's reliability and mean time to failure were calculated by using the universal generating function method where fuzzy variables follow the Weibull distribution. Yang [30] suggested a technique to develop the safety risk management in fabricated residential construction. The safety decisions become more accurate because this new technique helps to deal with uncertainty, indeterminacy, and inconsistency and the success of this technique was proved by a real-life case study. Zhang [31] examined the gent Garbage Sorting Cart using a decision-making approach and deals with the uncertainty in waste sorting. For this purpose, the Quadripartitioned Single-Valued Neutrosophic Z-Numbers (QSVNZN), CRITIC, and ARAS are combined. Zhao [32] evaluated the university dance teaching quality and established the triangular fuzzy neutrosophic number QUALIFLEX (TFNN-QUALIFLEX) to solve the attribute decision-making (MADM).

Renewable energy plants are very important as they generate electricity by using natural resources such as sunlight, wind, and water, and reduce their dependence on fossil fuels. Therefore, the reliability of renewable energy plants is also very important as it ensures regular power generation, reduces downtime, reduces maintenance costs, etc. But the traditional reliability assessment methods like Markovian and Semi-Markovian approaches do not properly deal with the uncertainty and imprecision present in the real-world failure data. The neutrosophic environment is used in the present study because it can deal with uncertain data more accurately. For the reliability analysis, the neutrosophic number can handle the uncertainty, imprecision, and indeterminacy more accurately. The accuracy of reliability was also improved by neutrosophic environment because it leads to better maintenance planning, risk management, and system optimization.

In this study, a model of a hydroelectric power plant was used to evaluate reliability and MTTF in a neutrosophic environment. From the introduction of the neutrosophic set and previous research, it was clearly found that the neutrosophic set can easily handle imprecise data where uncertainty is naturally combined into the set. By using universal generating function techniques and triangular neutrosophic numbers, this study can help to improve reliability and decision-making for hydroelectric power plant maintenance and operational efficiency. From the previous studies, it was noticed that no study of the hydroelectric power plant has been conducted in a neutrosophic environment. Thus, a mathematical model of a hydroelectric power plant was formed and analyzed its reliability and MTTF in the neutrosophic environment.

With knowledge of the above studies, we have introduced a new approach with some additional efforts, which include:

- The reliability of the hydroelectric power plant was first analyzed in the neutrosophic environment by using a universal generating function.
- Conventional reliability studies use probabilistic approaches, but this study deals with Weibull distribution in the neutrosophic environment.
- The study provides a graphical representation of triangular neutrosophic numbers and MTTF making results more explainable.

There are 6 sections in this paper. Section 1 consists of all the related previous studies with the novelty and motivation of our study. Section 2 contains preliminary concepts. The description of hydroelectric power plant was explained in Section 3. Section 4 shows the methodologies used for the study. Numerical results and limitations are considered in Section 5 and consequently, conclusions are considered in Section 6.

2. Preliminaries

2.1 Fuzzy Set

For a given non-empty set H , the fuzzy set $\tilde{\mathbb{R}}$ is defined as:

$$\tilde{\mathbb{R}} = \{ \langle \tilde{h}, \mu_{\tilde{\mathbb{R}}}(\tilde{h}) \rangle / \tilde{h} \in H \} \tag{1}$$

Where $\mu_{\tilde{\mathbb{R}}}(\tilde{h})$ is the membership function such that $\mu_{\tilde{\mathbb{R}}}(\tilde{h}): H \rightarrow [0,1]$.

2.2 Fuzzy Number

For the universal set of real numbers \mathbb{R} , a fuzzy set $\tilde{\mathbb{R}}$ is called fuzzy number if the membership function $\mu_{\tilde{\mathbb{R}}}$ of $\tilde{\mathbb{R}}$ follow the following conditions:

- i. $\mu_{\tilde{\mathbb{R}}}(\tilde{h}): H \rightarrow [0,1]$ is continuous
- ii. $\mu_{\tilde{\mathbb{R}}}(\tilde{h}) = 0$, for all $\tilde{h} \in (-\infty, a] \cup [d, \infty)$
- iii. $\mu_{\tilde{\mathbb{R}}}(\tilde{h})$ is strictly increasing on $[a, b]$ and strictly decreasing on $[c, d]$
- iv. $\mu_{\tilde{\mathbb{R}}}(\tilde{h}) = 1$, for all $\tilde{h} \in [b, c]$, where $a \leq b \leq c \leq d$.

2.3 Triangular Fuzzy Number

For a triangular fuzzy number (TFN), $\tilde{\mathbb{R}}$ is represented as $\tilde{\mathbb{R}} = (p, q, r)$ with the membership function $\mu_{\tilde{\mathbb{R}}}(\tilde{h})$

$$\mu_{\tilde{\mathbb{R}}}(\tilde{h}) = \begin{cases} 0 & \text{if } \tilde{h} < p \\ \frac{\tilde{h}-p}{q-p} & \text{if } p \leq \tilde{h} \leq q \\ \frac{r-\tilde{h}}{r-q} & \text{if } q \leq \tilde{h} \leq r \\ 0 & \text{if } \tilde{h} > r \end{cases} \tag{2}$$

Where p : lower bound

q : peak point

r : upper bound and $p \leq q \leq r$.

2.4 Intuitionistic Fuzzy Set

For a given set H , an intuitionistic fuzzy set (IFS) is defined as:

$$\tilde{\mathbb{R}}^I = \{ \langle \tilde{h}, \mu_{\tilde{\mathbb{R}}^I}(\tilde{h}), \nu_{\tilde{\mathbb{R}}^I}(\tilde{h}) \rangle / \tilde{h} \in H \} \tag{3}$$

Where $\mu_{\tilde{\mathbb{R}}^I}(\tilde{h})$ is the membership function, $\nu_{\tilde{\mathbb{R}}^I}(\tilde{h})$ is the non-membership function, $\mu_{\tilde{\mathbb{R}}^I}(\tilde{h}): H \rightarrow [0,1]$, $\nu_{\tilde{\mathbb{R}}^I}(\tilde{h}): H \rightarrow [0,1]$, and $0 \leq \mu_{\tilde{\mathbb{R}}^I}(\tilde{h}) + \nu_{\tilde{\mathbb{R}}^I}(\tilde{h}) \leq 1$.

For every IFS $\tilde{\mathbb{R}}^I$ in H ,

$\pi_{\tilde{\mathbb{R}}^I}(\tilde{h}) = 1 - \mu_{\tilde{\mathbb{R}}^I}(\tilde{h}) - \nu_{\tilde{\mathbb{R}}^I}(\tilde{h})$ is the intuitionistic fuzzy index of \tilde{h} in H .

Where $\pi_{\tilde{\mathbb{R}}^I}(\tilde{h})$ is the hesitancy degree.

2.5 Triangular Intuitionistic Fuzzy Number

A triangular intuitionistic fuzzy number (TIFN) is represented as:

$\tilde{\mathbb{R}}^I_{TIFN} = (a_1, a_2, a_3, a'_1, a'_2, a'_3)$, where triplet (a_1, a_2, a_3) shows membership function and (a'_1, a'_2, a'_3) shows non-membership function.

$$\text{Membership function: } \mu_{\tilde{\mathbb{R}}^I}(\tilde{h}) = \begin{cases} \frac{\tilde{h}-a_1}{a_2-a_1} & \text{for } a_1 \leq \tilde{h} \leq a_2 \\ \frac{a_3-\tilde{h}}{a_3-a_2} & \text{for } a_2 \leq \tilde{h} \leq a_3 \\ 0 & \text{otherwise} \end{cases} \quad (4)$$

$$\text{Non-membership function: } \nu_{\tilde{\mathbb{R}}^I}(\tilde{h}) = \begin{cases} \frac{a_2-x}{a_2-a'_1} & \text{for } a'_1 \leq x \leq a_2 \\ \frac{x-a_2}{a'_3-a_2} & \text{for } a_2 \leq x \leq a'_3 \\ 0 & \text{otherwise} \end{cases} \quad (5)$$

Where, $a'_1 \leq a_1 \leq a_2 \leq a_3 \leq a'_3$ and $\mu_{\tilde{\mathbb{R}}^I}(x) + \nu_{\tilde{\mathbb{R}}^I}(x) \leq 1$

2.6 Neutrosophic Set

For a given universal set H , the neutrosophic set $\tilde{\mathbb{R}}^{NS}$ is defined as:

$$\tilde{\mathbb{R}}^{NS} = \langle (\tilde{h}; T_{\tilde{\mathbb{R}}^{NS}}(\tilde{h}), I_{\tilde{\mathbb{R}}^{NS}}(\tilde{h}), F_{\tilde{\mathbb{R}}^{NS}}(\tilde{h})) : \tilde{h} \in H \rangle \quad (6)$$

Where, $T_{\tilde{\mathbb{R}}^{NS}}(\tilde{h}), I_{\tilde{\mathbb{R}}^{NS}}(\tilde{h}), F_{\tilde{\mathbb{R}}^{NS}}(\tilde{h})$ are truth membership, indeterminacy membership, falsity membership grade of \tilde{h} in $\tilde{\mathbb{R}}^{NS}$ which are real standard or non-standard subsets of $]0^-, 1^+[$ and $\mu_T(\tilde{h}) + \nu_I(\tilde{h}) + \sigma_F(\tilde{h}) \leq 3^+$.

2.7 Single Valued Linear Neutrosophic Number (SVTNN) (Chakraborty et al. [18])

A triangular single valued neutrosophic number is represented as: $\tilde{\mathbb{R}}^I_{SVTNN} = (\varepsilon_1, \varepsilon_2, \varepsilon_3; \varphi_1, \varphi_2, \varphi_3; \omega_1, \omega_2, \omega_3)$, where the quantity of the truth, indeterminacy, falsity are not dependent. The truth membership, indeterminacy membership, and falsity membership functions defined as follows:

$$T_{\tilde{\mathbb{R}}^{SVTNN}}(\tilde{h}) = \begin{cases} \frac{\tilde{h}-\varepsilon_1}{\varepsilon_2-\varepsilon_1} & \text{if } \varepsilon_1 \leq \tilde{h} < \varepsilon_2 \\ 1 & \text{if } \tilde{h} = \varepsilon_2 \\ \frac{\varepsilon_3-\tilde{h}}{\varepsilon_3-\varepsilon_2} & \text{if } \varepsilon_2 < \tilde{h} \leq \varepsilon_3 \\ 0 & \text{otherwise} \end{cases} \quad (7)$$

$$I_{\mathbb{R}SVTNN}(\tilde{h}) = \begin{cases} \frac{\varphi_2 - \tilde{h}}{\varphi_2 - \varphi_1} & \text{if } \varphi_1 \leq \tilde{h} < \varphi_2 \\ 0 & \text{if } \tilde{h} = \varphi_2 \\ \frac{\tilde{h} - \varphi_2}{\varphi_3 - \varphi_2} & \text{if } \varphi_2 < \tilde{h} \leq \varphi_3 \\ 1 & \text{otherwise} \end{cases} \tag{8}$$

$$F_{\mathbb{R}SVTNN}(\tilde{h}) = \begin{cases} \frac{\omega_2 - \tilde{h}}{\omega_2 - \omega_1} & \text{if } \omega_1 \leq \tilde{h} < \omega_2 \\ 0 & \text{if } \tilde{h} = \omega_2 \\ \frac{\tilde{h} - \omega_2}{\omega_3 - \omega_2} & \text{if } \omega_2 < \tilde{h} \leq \omega_3 \\ 1 & \text{otherwise} \end{cases} \tag{9}$$

Where $0 \leq T_{\mathbb{R}NS}(\tilde{h}) + I_{\mathbb{R}NS}(\tilde{h}) + F_{\mathbb{R}NS}(\tilde{h}) \leq 3$, $\tilde{h} \in \mathbb{R}NS$

2.8 (α, β, γ) -Cuts or (α, β, γ) -Level Intervals

The (α, β, γ) -cut set is defined as the crisp set of elements \tilde{h} satisfying the following conditions:

- i. The degree of truth membership $T_{\mathbb{R}NS}(\tilde{h})$ is at least α : $T_{\mathbb{R}NS}(\tilde{h}) \geq \alpha$.
- ii. The degree of indeterminacy membership $I_{\mathbb{R}NS}(\tilde{h})$ is at most β : $I_{\mathbb{R}NS}(\tilde{h}) \leq \beta$.
- iii. The degree of falsity membership $F_{\mathbb{R}NS}(\tilde{h})$ is at most γ : $F_{\mathbb{R}NS}(\tilde{h}) \leq \gamma$.

$$\tilde{\mathbb{R}}_{\alpha, \beta, \gamma}^{NS} = \left\{ \left(\tilde{h}, T_{\mathbb{R}TNN}(\tilde{h}), I_{\mathbb{R}TNN}(\tilde{h}), F_{\mathbb{R}TNN}(\tilde{h}) \right) : \tilde{h} \in H, \right. \\ \left. T_{\mathbb{R}TNN}(\tilde{h}) \geq \alpha, I_{\mathbb{R}TNN}(\tilde{h}) \leq \beta, F_{\mathbb{R}TNN}(\tilde{h}) \leq \gamma, \alpha, \beta, \gamma \in [0,1] \right\} \tag{10}$$

Where $\alpha, \beta, \gamma \in [0,1]$ and $\alpha + \beta + \gamma \leq 1$.

2.9 Weibull Distribution (Chachra et al. [29])

The Weibull Distribution is one of the most used distributions in reliability analysis. Weibull's probability density function is given as:

$$f(t) = \begin{cases} \frac{\delta}{\theta} \left(\frac{t}{\theta}\right)^{\delta-1} \exp\left\{-\left(\frac{t}{\theta}\right)^\delta\right\}, & x > 0, \theta > 0, \delta > 0 \\ 0, & \text{otherwise} \end{cases} \tag{11}$$

Where θ is a scale parameter and δ is a shape parameter.

The hazard function is defined as,

$$h(t) = \lim_{\Delta t \rightarrow 0} \frac{P(t < x < t + \Delta t)}{\Delta t} = \frac{f(t)}{R(t)}$$

The fuzzy hazard function is given by,

$$h(t) = \frac{\delta}{\theta} \left(\frac{t}{\theta}\right)^{\delta-1} \tag{12}$$

The reliability function can be formed as:

$$\begin{aligned}
 R(t) &= \int_t^\infty f(x)dx \\
 R(t) &= \int_t^\infty \frac{\delta}{\theta} \left(\frac{t}{\theta}\right)^{\delta-1} \exp\left\{-\left(\frac{t}{\theta}\right)^\delta\right\} dx. \\
 R(t) &= \exp\left\{-\left(\frac{t}{\theta}\right)^\delta\right\}
 \end{aligned}
 \tag{13}$$

2.10 Neutrosophic Weibull Distribution (Alhasan and Smarandache [20])

According to Weibull distribution of 3 parameters, the probability density function is given as:

$$f(t; T_\theta, I_\theta, F_\theta, T_\delta, I_\delta, F_\delta, T_t, I_t, F_t) = \begin{cases} \frac{T_\delta}{T_\theta} \left(\frac{T_t}{T_\theta}\right)^{T_\delta-1} \exp\left(-\left(\frac{T_t}{T_\theta}\right)^{T_\delta}\right), & t > 0, \theta > 0, \delta > 0 \\ 0, & \text{otherwise} \end{cases}
 \tag{14}$$

Where

- i. $T_\theta, I_\theta, F_\theta$ denotes the truth, indeterminacy, and falsity components of the scale parameter θ .
- ii. $T_\delta, I_\delta, F_\delta$ denotes the truth, indeterminacy, and falsity components of the shape parameter δ .
- iii. T_t, I_t, F_t denotes the truth, indeterminacy, and falsity components of the random variable t .

The hazard function is defined as the ratio of the probability density function $f(t; T_\theta, I_\theta, F_\theta, T_\delta, I_\delta, F_\delta, T_t, I_t, F_t)$ to the survival function $R(t; T_\theta, I_\theta, F_\theta, T_\delta, I_\delta, F_\delta, T_t, I_t, F_t)$

$$h(t; T_\theta, I_\theta, F_\theta, T_\delta, I_\delta, F_\delta, T_t, I_t, F_t) = \frac{f(t; T_\theta, I_\theta, F_\theta, T_\delta, I_\delta, F_\delta, T_t, I_t, F_t)}{R(t; T_\theta, I_\theta, F_\theta, T_\delta, I_\delta, F_\delta, T_t, I_t, F_t)}$$

The neutrosophic hazard function is given by,

$$h(t; T_\theta, I_\theta, F_\theta, T_\delta, I_\delta, F_\delta, T_t, I_t, F_t) = \frac{T_\delta}{T_\theta} \left(\frac{T_t}{T_\theta}\right)^{T_\delta-1}
 \tag{15}$$

where,

- i. T_θ denotes the truth membership of the scale parameter θ .
- ii. T_δ denotes the indeterminacy membership of the shape parameter δ .
- iii. T_t denotes the falsity membership of the random variable t .

2.11 Reliability Function

The neutrosophic reliability function of system is formed as follows:

$$\begin{aligned}
 R(t) &= \int_t^\infty f(x)dx \\
 R(t) &= \int_t^\infty \frac{T_\delta}{T_\theta} \left(\frac{T_t}{T_\theta}\right)^{T_\delta-1} \exp\left(-\left(\frac{T_t}{T_\theta}\right)^{T_\delta}\right) dx. \\
 R(t) &= \exp\left(-\left(\frac{T_t}{T_\theta}\right)^{T_\delta}\right)
 \end{aligned}
 \tag{16}$$

2.12 Neutrosophic Mean Time to Failure (Jamkhaneh [33])

Neutrosophic mean time to failure (NMTTF) is the estimated time to failure. Basically, it is an extension of fuzzy mean time to failure (FMTTF), including truth, indeterminacy, and falsity

components to handle uncertainty, imprecision, and inconsistency in failure time estimation. It is defined as:

$$NMTTF = \int_0^\infty R(t)dt : \theta \in \tilde{\theta}[\alpha, \beta, \gamma] \tag{17}$$

Where $R(t)$ is the reliability function of the hydroelectric power plant, $\tilde{\theta}[\alpha, \beta, \gamma]$ represents the neutrosophic parameters with α, β and γ as the truth, indeterminacy, and falsity membership functions.

2.13 Universal Generating Function (Chachra et al. [29])

The universal generating function was introduced by Ushakov, I.A. [34] in the context of mathematical combinatorics and formal power series. The UGF gives more flexibility in modeling multi-parameter or multi-dimensional situations by representing the sequences and functions in a more general form rather than traditional generating functions. It is a mathematical tool used to study complex systems dealing with probability distributions and reliability functions. The UGF uses recursive methods to solve complicated algorithms. In this study, the UGF is used to analyze the reliability of hydroelectric power plants.

Mathematical representation of UGF:

The UGF of independent discrete random variable is represented as $u(y) = \sum_{n=1}^N p_n y^{x_n}$, where N is the total number of possible values of random variable X , p_n is the probability related with each value x_n of random variable X , x_n denotes the value taken by the random variable in the n -th state, and y is a complex number used in the generating function.

UGF for series configuration

Let $u_h(y)$ and $u_k(y)$ are two u-functions of two components h and k connected in series configuration. The UGF is represented as:

$$u_h(y) \otimes_{ser} u_k(y) = \sum_{n=1}^{N_h} p_{hn} y^{x_{hn}} \otimes_{ser} \sum_{i=1}^{N_k} p_{ik} y^{x_{ik}} = \sum_{n=1}^{N_h} \sum_{i=1}^{N_k} p_{hn} p_{ik} y^{\min\{x_{hn}, x_{ik}\}} \tag{18}$$

UGF for parallel configuration

Let $u_h(y)$ and $u_k(y)$ are two u-functions of two components h and k connected in series configuration. The UGF is represented as:

$$u_h(y) \otimes_{par} u_k(y) = \sum_{n=1}^{N_h} p_{hn} y^{x_{hn}} \otimes_{par} \sum_{i=1}^{N_k} p_{ik} y^{x_{ik}} = \sum_{n=1}^{N_h} \sum_{i=1}^{N_k} p_{hn} p_{ik} y^{\max\{x_{hn}, x_{ik}\}} \tag{19}$$

3. System Description

In this section, a brief description of a hydroelectric power plant is given. A hydroelectric power plant consists of six subsystems: governor system, turbine, generator system, generator converter, excitation system, and main unit transformer. All the subsystems are arranged in a series configuration. The visual representation of subsystems is shown in Figure 1. The working of different subsystems of the hydroelectric power plant is described below:

Figure 1: Flow diagram of hydroelectric power plant

- i. **Governor system:** It limits the turbine speed and output power by controlling the flow of water to the turbine. To maintain the speed and frequency, the governor system senses the speed deviations in the turbine and adjusts the wicket gates. It consists of a single unit and connects in series with the turbine. Failure of this unit results in system failure.
- ii. **Turbine:** It converts the kinetic and potential energy of water into mechanical energy by spinning its blades. The turbine blades spin due to the flow of water over them. It consists of two units connected in parallel configuration with each other and in a series configuration with generator system.
- iii. **Generator system:** It converts the mechanical energy produced in a turbine to electrical energy. The rotor of the generator is driven by the rotating shaft connected to the turbine. It consists of a single unit and connects in series with a generator converter. Failure of this unit causes system failure.
- iv. **Generator converter:** To meet the grid requirements, it transforms the properties of electrical output like frequency and voltage. It consists of a single unit and connects in series with an excitation system. Failure of this unit causes system failure.
- v. **Excitation system:** To maintain a steady magnetic field, it supplies the required field current to the generator's rotor. It adjusts the DC supply to the rotor. It consists of a single unit and connects in series with the main unit transformer. Failure of this unit causes system failure.
- vi. **Main unit transformer:** It increases the generated voltage for long-distance transmission. It transforms the low electric output from the generator to high voltage for transmission. It consists of a single unit. Failure of this unit causes system failure.

4. Methodology

4.1 Reliability function using UGF method

The reliability function of the hydroelectric power plant is formed by UGF method. The failed and working states are represented by 0 and 1 respectively. Figure 2 shows the block diagram of hydroelectric power plant. A denotes governor system, B and C are two turbines, D denotes generator system, E is the generator converter, F is the excitation system, and G denotes main unit transformer.

Figure 2: Block diagram of hydroelectric power plant

The u-functions for all six subsystems are represented as:

$$\begin{aligned}
 A : u_1(y) &= P_1y^1 + (1 - P_1)y^0 \\
 B : u_2(y) &= P_2y^1 + (1 - P_2)y^0 \\
 C : u_3(y) &= P_3y^1 + (1 - P_3)y^0 \\
 D : u_4(y) &= P_4y^1 + (1 - P_4)y^0 \\
 E : u_5(y) &= P_5y^1 + (1 - P_5)y^0 \\
 F : u_6(y) &= P_6y^1 + (1 - P_6)y^0 \\
 G : u_7(y) &= P_7y^1 + (1 - P_7)y^0
 \end{aligned}$$

Where $P_i, i = 1, 2, \dots, 6$ is the probability of the i^{th} working component and $(1 - P_i), i = 1, 2, \dots, 6$ is the probability of the failed component.

Using Eq. (18) and (19), the UGF is formed as follows:

$$\begin{aligned}
 u_8(y) &= u_{2,3}(y) = u_2(y) \otimes_{max} u_3(y) \\
 u_{2,3}(y) &= P_2P_3y^1 + P_2(1 - P_3)y^1 + P_3(1 - P_2)y^1 + (1 - P_2)(1 - P_3)y^0
 \end{aligned} \tag{20}$$

The u-function of the system is:

$$u(y) = u_1(y) \otimes_{min} u_8(y) \otimes_{min} u_4(y) \otimes_{min} u_5(y) \otimes_{min} u_6(y) \otimes_{min} u_7(y) \tag{21}$$

The reliability is given by $u'(y)$ at $y = 1$. Hence, the reliability function of the hydroelectric power system is:

$$R = u'(1) = P_1P_2P_4P_5P_6P_7 + P_1P_2P_4P_5P_6P_7(1 - P_3) + P_1P_3P_4P_5P_6P_7(1 - P_2) \tag{22}$$

Since the subsystems are supposed to be independent and identically distributed, that is,

$$\begin{aligned}
 P_1 = P_2 = P_3 = P_4 = P_5 = P_6 = P_7 = r, \text{ then,} \\
 R = 2r^6 - r^7
 \end{aligned} \tag{23}$$

4.2 (α, β, γ) -Cuts or (α, β, γ) -Level Intervals

The triangular single valued neutrosophic number (SVTNN) used for truth, indeterminacy, and falsity membership is $\psi = (\varepsilon_1, \varepsilon_2, \varepsilon_3; \varphi_1, \varphi_2, \varphi_3; \omega_1, \omega_2, \omega_3) = (10, 15, 20; 14, 16, 22; 12, 15, 19)$. Based on this triangular input data, all the truth, indeterminacy, and falsity membership functions are attained on different α, β , and γ -cuts. By using equation (10), the α, β , and γ -cuts for triangular neutrosophic numbers are represented as:

$$\begin{aligned}
 T_{\mathbb{R}SVTNN}(\alpha - \text{cut}) &= [\varepsilon_1 + \alpha_1(\varepsilon_2 - \varepsilon_1), \varepsilon_3 - \alpha_2(\varepsilon_3 - \varepsilon_2)] \\
 T_{\mathbb{R}SVTNN}(\alpha - \text{cut}) &= [10 + 5\alpha_1, 20 - 5\alpha_2]
 \end{aligned} \tag{24}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 I_{\mathbb{R}SVTNN}(\beta - \text{cut}) &= [\varphi_2 - \beta_1(\varphi_2 - \varphi_1), \varphi_2 + \beta_2(\varphi_3 - \varphi_2)] \\
 I_{\mathbb{R}SVTNN}(\beta - \text{cut}) &= [16 - 2\beta_1, 16 + 6\beta_2]
 \end{aligned} \tag{25}$$

$$F_{\mathbb{R}SVTNN}(\gamma - \text{cut}) = [\omega_2 + \gamma_1(\omega_2 - \omega_1), \omega_2 - \gamma_2(\omega_3 - \omega_2)]$$

$$F_{\mathbb{R}SVTNN}(\gamma - \text{cut}) = [15 - 3\gamma_1, 15 + 4\gamma_2] \tag{26}$$

The values of $T_{\mathbb{R}TNN}(\alpha_1), T_{\mathbb{R}TNN}(\alpha_2), I_{\mathbb{R}TNN}(\beta_1), I_{\mathbb{R}TNN}(\beta_2), F_{\mathbb{R}TNN}(\gamma_1), F_{\mathbb{R}TNN}(\gamma_2)$ and graphical representation of triangular neutrosophic number (TNN) are shown in Table 1 and Figure 3.

Table 1: Values of $T_{\mathbb{R}TNN}(\alpha_1), T_{\mathbb{R}TNN}(\alpha_2), I_{\mathbb{R}TNN}(\beta_1), I_{\mathbb{R}TNN}(\beta_2), F_{\mathbb{R}TNN}(\gamma_1), F_{\mathbb{R}TNN}(\gamma_2)$.

α, β, γ	$T_{\mathbb{R}SVTNN}(\alpha_1)$	$T_{\mathbb{R}SVTNN}(\alpha_2)$	$I_{\mathbb{R}SVTNN}(\beta_1)$	$I_{\mathbb{R}SVTNN}(\beta_2)$	$F_{\mathbb{R}SVTNN}(\gamma_1)$	$F_{\mathbb{R}SVTNN}(\gamma_2)$
0	10	20	16	16	15	15
0.1	10.5	19.5	15.8	16.6	14.7	15.4
0.2	11	19	15.6	17.2	14.4	15.8
0.3	11.5	18.5	15.4	17.8	14.1	16.2
0.4	12	18	15.2	18.4	13.8	16.6
0.5	12.5	17.5	15	19	13.5	17
0.6	13	17	14.8	19.6	13.2	17.4
0.7	13.5	16.5	14.6	20.2	12.9	17.8
0.8	14	16	14.4	20.8	12.6	18.2
0.9	14.5	15.5	14.2	21.4	12.3	18.6
1	15	15	14	22	12	19

Figure 3: Graphical representation of triangular neutrosophic number $\psi = (10,15,20; 14,16,22; 12,15,19)$

4.3 Reliability Function

For triangular neutrosophic number, $\tilde{\mathbb{R}}^I_{SVTNN} = (\varepsilon_1, \varepsilon_2, \varepsilon_3; \varphi_1, \varphi_2, \varphi_3; \omega_1, \omega_2, \omega_3) = (10,15,20; 14,16,22; 12,15,19)$, the reliability functions for α, β , and γ cuts using equation (16) are represented as follows:

$$R_{SVTNN}(\alpha_1) = 2e^{-\left[\left(\frac{t}{10+5\alpha_1}\right)^\delta\right]^6} - e^{-\left[\left(\frac{t}{10+5\alpha_1}\right)^\delta\right]^7} \tag{27}$$

$$R_{SVTNN}(\alpha_2) = 2e^{-\left[\left(\frac{t}{20-5\alpha_2}\right)^\delta\right]^6} - e^{-\left[\left(\frac{t}{20-5\alpha_2}\right)^\delta\right]^7} \tag{28}$$

$$R_{SVTNN}(\beta_1) = 2e^{-\left[\left(\frac{t}{16-2\beta_1}\right)^\delta\right]^6} - e^{-\left[\left(\frac{t}{16-2\beta_1}\right)^\delta\right]^7} \tag{29}$$

$$R_{SVTNN}(\beta_2) = 2e^{-\left[\left(\frac{t}{16+6\beta_2}\right)^\delta\right]^6} - e^{-\left[\left(\frac{t}{16+6\beta_2}\right)^\delta\right]^7} \tag{30}$$

$$R_{SVTNN}(\gamma_1) = 2e^{-\left[\left(\frac{t}{15-3\gamma_1}\right)^\delta\right]^6} - e^{-\left[\left(\frac{t}{15-3\gamma_1}\right)^\delta\right]^7} \tag{31}$$

$$R_{SVTNN}(\gamma_2) = 2e^{-\left[\left(\frac{t}{15+4\gamma_2}\right)^\delta\right]^6} - e^{-\left[\left(\frac{t}{15+4\gamma_2}\right)^\delta\right]^7} \tag{32}$$

4.4 MTTF using TNN [Kumar and Singh (2015)]

When the lifetime follows neutrosophic Weibull distribution, then using equation (17), the neutrosophic mean time to failure cuts are represented as:

$$NMTTF = \{\theta\Gamma(1 + \delta^{-1}) | \theta \in \tilde{\theta}[\alpha, \beta, \gamma]\} \tag{33}$$

$$\begin{aligned} NMTTF(\alpha_1, \alpha_2) &= ((\varepsilon_1 + \alpha_1(\varepsilon_2 - \varepsilon_1))\Gamma(1 + \delta^{-1}), (\varepsilon_3 - \alpha_2(\varepsilon_3 - \varepsilon_2))\Gamma(1 + \delta^{-1})) \\ &= ((10 + 5\alpha_1)\Gamma(1 + \delta^{-1}), (20 - 5\alpha_2)\Gamma(1 + \delta^{-1})) \end{aligned} \tag{34}$$

$$\begin{aligned} NMTTF(\beta_1, \beta_2) &= ((\varphi_2 - \beta_1(\varphi_2 - \varphi_1))\Gamma(1 + \delta^{-1}), (\varphi_2 + \beta_2(\varphi_3 - \varphi_2))\Gamma(1 + \delta^{-1})) \\ &= ((16 - 2\beta_1)\Gamma(1 + \delta^{-1}), (16 + 6\beta_2)\Gamma(1 + \delta^{-1})) \end{aligned} \tag{35}$$

$$\begin{aligned} NMTTF(\gamma_1, \gamma_2) &= ((\omega_2 + \gamma_1(\omega_2 - \omega_1))\Gamma(1 + \delta^{-1}), (\omega_2 - \gamma_2(\omega_3 - \omega_2))\Gamma(1 + \delta^{-1})) \\ &= ((15 - 3\gamma_1)\Gamma(1 + \delta^{-1}), (15 + 4\gamma_2)\Gamma(1 + \delta^{-1})) \end{aligned} \tag{36}$$

5. Results

Neutrosophic fuzzy sets have a unique ability to handle uncertainty, imprecision, and indeterminacy in real-world situations over traditional fuzzy sets. A neutrosophic fuzzy set is an extension of traditional fuzzy sets and introduces three components truth, indeterminacy, and falsity, making it more flexible than traditional fuzzy sets which only work on truth value. It handles the uncertainty in a better way and describes complex systems more clearly. In an uncertain environment, the indeterminacy and falsity components provide more reliable and strong decision-making.

5.1 Single Valued Triangular Neutrosophic Reliability

In this study, the reliability function of hydroelectric power plant was formed by using universal generating method and reliability was analyzed over three specific time points $t=0, t=5$, and $t=10$, and

three value of shape parameter $\delta=0.8, \delta=0.9, \delta=1$ with the increment of 0.1 in the values of $\alpha, \beta,$ and γ from the interval $[0,1]$.

Table 2: Neutrosophic reliability of hydroelectric plants using TNN at $\delta =0.8$ and $t=0,5,10$.

$\delta =0.8$	t=0			t=5			t=10		
α, β, γ	R ($\alpha 1, \alpha 2$)	R ($\beta 1, \beta 2$)	R ($\gamma 1, \gamma 2$)	R ($\alpha 1, \alpha 2$)	R ($\beta 1, \beta 2$)	R ($\gamma 1, \gamma 2$)	R ($\alpha 1, \alpha 2$)	R ($\beta 1, \beta 2$)	R ($\gamma 1, \gamma 2$)
0	(1.0,1.0)	(1.0,1.0)	(1.0,1.0)	(0.739468, 0.986338)	(0.962796, 0.962796)	(0.950563, 0.950563)	(2.62E-07, 0.536486)	(0.215943, 0.215943)	(0.133235, 0.133235)
0.1	(1.0,1.0)	(1.0,1.0)	(1.0,1.0)	(0.782842, 0.984676)	(0.960667, 0.968406)	(0.945998, 0.955957)	(7.16E-06, 0.501425)	(0.198905, 0.267542)	(0.110383, 0.16542)
0.2	(1.0,1.0)	(1.0,1.0)	(1.0,1.0)	(0.818583, 0.982764)	(0.958391, 0.973035)	(0.940927, 0.960667)	(8.77E-05, 0.464516)	(0.182041, 0.318951)	(0.089027, 0.1989)
0.3	(1.0,1.0)	(1.0,1.0)	(1.0,1.0)	(0.847965, 0.98056)	(0.955957, 0.976876)	(0.935284, 0.964789)	(0.000595, 0.425892)	(0.165422, 0.369303)	(0.069546, 0.2331)
0.4	(1.0,1.0)	(1.0,1.0)	(1.0,1.0)	(0.872115, 0.978008)	(0.953352, 0.980079)	(0.928996, 0.968406)	(0.002587, 0.385739)	(0.149124, 0.417977)	(0.052301, 0.26754)
0.5	(1.0,1.0)	(1.0,1.0)	(1.0,1.0)	(0.891994, 0.975044)	(0.950563, 0.982764)	(0.921979, 0.971588)	(0.008016, 0.344302)	(0.133235, 0.464516)	(0.037596, 0.3019)
0.6	(1.0,1.0)	(1.0,1.0)	(1.0,1.0)	(0.908398, 0.971588)	(0.947573, 0.985027)	(0.914137, 0.974395)	(0.019161, 0.301895)	(0.117852, 0.508588)	(0.025616, 0.33589)
0.7	(1.0,1.0)	(1.0,1.0)	(1.0,1.0)	(0.921979, 0.967545)	(0.944367, 0.986941)	(0.905362, 0.976876)	(0.037596, 0.258927)	(0.103079, 0.549972)	(0.016381, 0.3693)
0.8	(1.0,1.0)	(1.0,1.0)	(1.0,1.0)	(0.933264, 0.962796)	(0.940927, 0.988569)	(0.89553, 0.979074)	(0.063532, 0.215943)	(0.089027, 0.588546)	(0.009721, 0.40197)

0.9	(1.0,1.0)	(1.0,1.0)	(1.0,1.0)	(0.942678, 0.957195)	(0.937233, 0.989958)	(0.8845, 0.981026)	(0.095956, 0.173696)	(0.075808, 0.624272)	(0.005282, 0.43375)
1	(1.0,1.0)	(1.0,1.0)	(1.0,1.0)	(0.950563, 0.950563)	(0.933264, 0.99115)	(0.872115, 0.982764)	(0.133235, 0.133235)	(0.063532, 0.657185)	(0.00259, 0.46452)

The reliability of hydroelectric power plant for SVTNN with three specific time points $t=0$, $t=5$, and $t=10$, and three values of shape parameter $\delta=0.8, \delta=0.9, \delta=1$ was shown in Table 2, 3, and 4. The neutrosophic reliability for $\delta=0.8$ is (1.0,1.0) at $\alpha, \beta, \gamma=1$, and $t=0$, (0.950563, 0.950563) at $\alpha=1$, and $t=5$, (0.962796, 0.962796) at $\beta=0$ and $t=5$, (0.950563, 0.950563) at $\gamma=0$ and $t=5$, (0.133235, 0.133235) at $\alpha=1$, and $t=10$, (0.215943, 0.215943) at $\beta=0$ and $t=10$, (0.133235, 0.133235) at $\gamma=0$ and $t=10$.

Table 3: Neutrosophic reliability of hydroelectric plants using TNN at $\delta = 0.9$ and $t=0,5,10$.

$\delta = 0.9$	$t=0$			$t=5$			$t=10$		
α, β, γ	R ($\alpha 1, \alpha 2$)	R ($\beta 1, \beta 2$)	R ($\gamma 1, \gamma 2$)	R ($\alpha 1, \alpha 2$)	R ($\beta 1, \beta 2$)	R ($\gamma 1, \gamma 2$)	R ($\alpha 1, \alpha 2$)	R ($\beta 1, \beta 2$)	R ($\gamma 1, \gamma 2$)
0	(1.0,1.0)	(1.0,1.0)	(1.0,1.0)	(0.91778, 0.99755)	(0.99221, 0.99221)	(0.98915, 0.98915)	(0.03067, 0.88167)	(0.68868, 0.68868)	(0.60334, 0.60334)
0.1	(1.0,1.0)	(1.0,1.0)	(1.0,1.0)	(0.93504, 0.9972)	(0.99169, 0.99356)	(0.98797, 0.99052)	(0.06878, 0.86697)	(0.6730, 0.73133)	(0.57408, 0.6397)
0.2	(1.0,1.0)	(1.0,1.0)	(1.0,1.0)	(0.94825, 0.9968)	(0.99113, 0.99464)	(0.98663, 0.99169)	(0.12122, 0.85022)	(0.65676, 0.76818)	(0.54314, 0.67308)
0.3	(1.0,1.0)	(1.0,1.0)	(1.0,1.0)	(0.95845, 0.99632)	(0.99052, 0.99551)	(0.98512, 0.9927)	(0.18252, 0.83112)	(0.6397, 0.79985)	(0.51056, 0.70358)
0.4	(1.0,1.0)	(1.0,1.0)	(1.0,1.0)	(0.96639, 0.99576)	(0.98986, 0.99622)	(0.9834, 0.99356)	(0.24782, 0.80937)	(0.6219, 0.827)	(0.47641, 0.73133)
0.5	(1.0,1.0)	(1.0,1.0)	(1.0,1.0)	(0.97261, 0.9951)	(0.98915, 0.9968)	(0.98143, 0.9943)	(0.31388, 0.78462)	(0.60334, 0.85022)	(0.44081, 0.7565)
0.6	(1.0,1.0)	(1.0,1.0)	(1.0,1.0)	(0.97752, 0.9943)	(0.98838, 0.99728)	(0.97919, 0.99495)	(0.37867, 0.7565)	(0.58402, 0.87006)	(0.4039, 0.77928)
0.7	(1.0,1.0)	(1.0,1.0)	(1.0,1.0)	(0.98143, 0.99335)	(0.98754, 0.99767)	(0.97663, 0.99551)	(0.44081, 0.72464)	(0.56396, 0.88704)	(0.36589, 0.79985)

0.8	(1.0,1.0)	(1.0,1.0)	(1.0,1.0)	(0.98457, 0.99221)	(0.98663, 0.998)	(0.97369, 0.996)	(0.49935, 0.68868)	(0.54314, 0.90156)	(0.32699 ,0.81841)
0.9	(1.0,1.0)	(1.0,1.0)	(1.0,1.0)	(0.9871, 0.99083)	(0.98564, 0.99828)	(0.9703, 0.99642)	(0.55364, 0.64832)	(0.5216, 0.91401)	(0.28752 ,0.83514)
1	(1.0,1.0)	(1.0,1.0)	(1.0,1.0)	(0.98915, 0.98915)	(0.98457, 0.99851)	(0.96639, 0.9968)	(0.60334, 0.60334)	(0.49935, 0.9247)	(0.24782 ,0.85022)

For $\delta = 0.9$, the neutrosophic reliability is (1.0,1.0) at $\alpha, \beta, \gamma=1$, and $t=0$, (0.98915,0.98915) at $\alpha=1$ and $t=5$, (0.99221,0.99221) at $\beta=0$ and $t=5$, (0.98915,0.98915) at $\gamma=0$ and $t=5$, (0.60334,0.60334) at $\alpha=1$ and $t=10$, (0.68868,0.68868) at $\beta=0$ and $t=10$, (0.98915,0.98915) at $\gamma=0$ and $t=10$.

Table 4: Neutrosophic reliability of hydroelectric plants using TNN at $\delta = 2$ and $t=0,5,10$.

$\delta = 1$	$t=0$			$t=5$			$t=10$		
α, β, γ	R ($\alpha 1,$ $\alpha 2$)	R ($\beta 1,$ $\beta 2$)	R ($\gamma 1,$ $\gamma 2$)	R ($\alpha 1, \alpha 2$)	R ($\beta 1, \beta 2$)	R ($\gamma 1, \gamma 2$)	R ($\alpha 1, \alpha 2$)	R ($\beta 1, \beta 2$)	R ($\gamma 1, \gamma 2$)
0	(1.0,1.0)	(1.0,1.0)	(1.0,1.0)	(0.97677, 0.99957)	(0.99842, 0.99842)	(0.99771, 0.99771)	(0.36787, 0.97677)	(0.92084, 0.92084)	(0.8887, 0.88875)
0.1	(1.0,1.0)	(1.0,1.0)	(1.0,1.0)	(0.98235, 0.9995)	(0.99831, 0.99873)	(0.99743, 0.99803)	(0.45701, 0.97323)	(0.91535, 0.93504)	(0.87649, 0.90306)
0.2	(1.0,1.0)	(1.0,1.0)	(1.0,1.0)	(0.98643, 0.99942)	(0.99818, 0.99896)	(0.9971, 0.99831)	(0.53871, 0.96906)	(0.90944, 0.94643)	(0.86273, 0.91535)
0.3	(1.0,1.0)	(1.0,1.0)	(1.0,1.0)	(0.98946, 0.99932)	(0.99803, 0.99915)	(0.99673, 0.99853)	(0.61134, 0.96412)	(0.90306, 0.9556)	(0.84731, 0.92593)
0.4	(1.0,1.0)	(1.0,1.0)	(1.0,1.0)	(0.99173, 0.9992)	(0.99788, 0.9993)	(0.99629, 0.99873)	(0.67434, 0.95825)	(0.89617, 0.96302)	(0.83001, 0.93504)
0.5	(1.0,1.0)	(1.0,1.0)	(1.0,1.0)	(0.99346, 0.99906)	(0.99771, 0.99942)	(0.99579, 0.99889)	(0.72798, 0.95126)	(0.88875, 0.96906)	(0.81063, 0.94291)
0.6	(1.0,1.0)	(1.0,1.0)	(1.0,1.0)	(0.99478, 0.99889)	(0.99753, 0.99951)	(0.99521, 0.99903)	(0.77306, 0.94291)	(0.88073, 0.97399)	(0.78893, 0.94971)
0.7	(1.0,1.0)	(1.0,1.0)	(1.0,1.0)	(0.99579, 0.99868)	(0.99732, 0.99959)	(0.99454, 0.99915)	(0.81063, 0.93289)	(0.87208, 0.97803)	(0.76468, 0.9556)

0.8	(1.0,1.0)	(1.0,1.0)	(1.0,1.0)	(0.99659, 0.99842)	(0.9971, 0.99966)	(0.99375, 0.99925)	(0.84176, 0.92084)	(0.86273, 0.98137)	(0.73765, 0.96072)
0.9	(1.0,1.0)	(1.0,1.0)	(1.0,1.0)	(0.99722, 0.99811)	(0.99686, 0.99971)	(0.99282, 0.99934)	(0.86749, 0.90631)	(0.85265, 0.98413)	(0.7076, 0.96517)
1	(1.0,1.0)	(1.0,1.0)	(1.0,1.0)	(0.99771, 0.99771)	(0.99659, 0.99975)	(0.99173, 0.99942)	(0.88875, 0.88875)	(0.84176, 0.98643)	(0.67434, 0.96906)

For $\delta = 1$, the neutrosophic reliability is (1.0,1.0) at $\alpha, \beta, \gamma = 1$, and $t = 0$, (0.99771,0.99771) at $\alpha = 1$ and $t = 5$, (0.99842,0.99842) at $\beta = 0$ and $t = 5$, (0.99771,0.99771) at $\gamma = 0$ and $t = 5$, (0.88875,0.88875) at $\alpha = 1$ and $t = 10$, (0.92084,0.92084) at $\beta = 0$ and $t = 10$, (0.88875,0.88875) at $\gamma = 0$ and $t = 10$.

5.2 MTTF using Triangular Neutrosophic Set

The neutrosophic MTTF for hydroelectric power plant is achieved by using equation (MTTF) and (cut sets). The MTTF for $\delta = 0.8$ is (16.995, 16.995) at $\alpha = 1$, (18.128,18.128) at $\beta = 0$, and (16.995,16.995) at $\gamma = 0$. The neutrosophic MTTF is obtained at $\delta = 0.8$ and it is shown in Table 5 and Figure 4.

Table 5: Neutrosophic MTTF using TNN

α, β, γ	MTTF ($\alpha 1, \alpha 2$)	MTTF ($\beta 1, \beta 2$)	MTTF ($\gamma 1, \gamma 2$)
0	(11.33, 22.6601)	(18.128,18.128)	(16.995,16.995)
0.1	(11.8965, 22.0936)	(17.9014,18.8079)	(16.6551,17.4482)
0.2	(12.463, 21.5271)	(17.6748,19.4877)	(16.3152,17.9014)
0.3	(13.0295, 20.9606)	(17.4482,20.1675)	(15.9753,18.3547)
0.4	(13.596, 20.3941)	(17.2216,20.8473)	(15.6354,18.8079)
0.5	(14.1625, 19.8276)	(16.995,21.5271)	(15.2955,19.2611)
0.6	(14.729, 19.2611)	(16.7684,22.2069)	(14.9556,19.7143)
0.7	(15.2955, 18.6946)	(16.5418,22.8867)	(14.6157,20.1675)
0.8	(15.862, 18.128)	(16.3152,23.5665)	(14.2758,20.6207)
0.9	(16.4285, 17.5615)	(16.0886,24.2463)	(13.9359,21.0739)
1	(16.995, 16.995)	(15.862,24.9261)	(13.596,21.5271)

Figure 3: Graphical representation of MTTF using SVTNN

6. Conclusion

Reliability of any industrial system is a very important factor in performance evaluation and theory of uncertainty plays a key role in system modeling. For the situations having high uncertainty, fuzzy reliability can play a significant role. In this present study, we define the concept of triangular neutrosophic number and implement it on a hydroelectric power plant to estimate the reliability and MTTF where each neutrosophic variable follows Weibull distribution which was not defined earlier. The reliability function is formed by using a universal generating function. Table 1 to 5 demonstrates all the outcome results for reliability and MTTF. At $\delta = 1$ and $t = 5$, the reliability reaches its maximum value that is 0.99975 for $R(\alpha_1, \alpha_2)$ and MTTF attains its maximum value 24.9261. Numerical, as well as graphical methods, are used to represent triangular neutrosophic numbers and MTTF. The neutrosophic fuzzy methodology was used because it can handle uncertainty, imprecision, and indeterminacy easily and provide more accurate and flexible results for reliability and MTTF. As compared to the traditional reliability methods, the neutrosophic approach used in this study can deal with high level of uncertainties. Similarly, as compared to crisp or fuzzy reliability approaches, this neutrosophic fuzzy approach has more flexible and precise calculations of the system behavior. The above study is helpful in many fields and for future studies, but it has also contained some limitations like Weibull distribution used in this study may not be always optimal for real-world failure patterns. This study only considers the reliability and MTTF factors, but there are also many parameters like availability, maintainability, cost-related factors etc., which are also useful for reliability evaluation. The methodology used in the study is not validated for other industries like healthcare, aerospace etc. The methodologies used in this study and the results can be used in future for finding the behaviour of the system. These techniques can be used in other sectors like aerospace, healthcare, etc., as well as other neutrosophic numbers like trapezoidal neutrosophic numbers can also be used in the future. To improve real-time fault detection, the combination of neutrosophic

fuzzy reliability and machine learning can be used. Therefore, this study is very useful for future researchers who deal with system modeling with uncertainty.

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